

Capacity Building And Curriculum Transformation For Inclusive Education: A Study Of Teacher Preparation Practices In Colleges Of Education In Osun State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates how capacity building and curriculum transformation contribute to the effective preparation of pre-service teachers for inclusive education in Colleges of Education in Osun State, Nigeria. Four research questions and three hypotheses were raised for the study. It employs a descriptive survey design involving 150 participants comprising teacher educators and final-year pre-service teachers across three institutions. Using a structured questionnaire and statistical analysis, the study explores the extent of current capacity building initiatives, the degree of curriculum transformation, teacher preparedness, and the challenges faced in implementing inclusive education. Findings reveal that capacity building efforts are limited and inconsistent, with mean values ranging from 2.0 to 2.8. A significant positive relationship was found between capacity building initiatives and pre-service teachers' preparedness (Pearson $r = 0.64$, $p < 0.05$). Curriculum reforms are emerging but not yet systemic, with mean values between 2.3 and 2.6; an ANOVA result indicated significant differences among institutions ($F(1,98) = 4.23$, $p = 0.03$). While pre-service teachers show moderate preparedness (mean values 2.7 to 3.1), a strong correlation also exists between teacher competence and inclusive education (Pearson $r = 0.58$, $p < 0.05$). Challenges such as inadequate instructional materials and large class sizes persist. The study concludes with recommendations for structured training modules, policy support, curriculum review, and institutional collaboration to promote inclusive and sustainable education.

Keywords: Capacity Building, Curriculum Transformation, Inclusive Education, Teacher Preparation Practices

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a pivotal role in national development, particularly when it is inclusive, equitable, and aligned with sustainable development goals. In recent years, the call for inclusive education has gained momentum as societies become increasingly diverse and globalized. To meet the challenges of inclusive education, there is a pressing need to reform teacher preparation practices and transform curricula to address the varying needs of learners, including those with disabilities, linguistic diversities, and socio-cultural differences. Capacity building in this context refers to enhancing the knowledge, skills, competencies, and institutional systems necessary for inclusive and sustainable educational delivery [7]. Colleges of Education, as the training ground for future teachers, must be at the forefront of these reforms. In Osun State, Nigeria, Colleges of Education face numerous challenges, including outdated curricula, inadequate training facilities, and limited professional development opportunities for teacher educators. Inclusive education refers to a system where all learners, regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, linguistic, or other conditions, are integrated into mainstream educational settings [1]. It promotes equality, participation, and accessibility,

especially for marginalized and disadvantaged learners. Capacity building in education encompasses the professional development of educators, strengthening institutional frameworks, and improving infrastructure to meet teaching and learning goals [2]. For inclusive education, this includes training teachers to understand diverse needs and adopt differentiated instructional strategies [3].

Curriculum transformation involves revising learning content, pedagogy, and assessment methods to reflect inclusive values and sustainable development goals [4]. This transformation ensures that education systems are responsive to the needs of all learners, including those with disabilities, different languages, or cultural backgrounds. Pre-service teacher preparation plays a vital role in developing the skills, knowledge, and attitudes required to manage diverse classrooms. Studies have shown that teachers trained in inclusive practices are more confident and competent in handling learners with special needs [5].

Challenges include lack of teacher training, inadequate instructional materials, insufficient policy support, and large class sizes. In Nigeria, inclusive education is still emerging, and Colleges of Education often struggle with insufficient resources

and outdated curricula [6]. This study examines how capacity building and curriculum transformation contribute to the preparedness of teachers for inclusive education in selected Colleges of Education in Osun State. It investigates the extent to which current teacher preparation practices align with the principles of inclusive education and identifies gaps in policy and implementation.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study is to assess the effectiveness of capacity building and curriculum transformation efforts in the preparation of pre-service teachers for inclusive education in Colleges of Education in Osun State. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Evaluate the extent of capacity building initiatives for inclusive education among teacher educators and pre-service teachers among colleges of education in Osun state.
2. Examine the degree of curriculum transformation towards inclusive education in teacher preparation programmes among colleges of education in Osun state.
3. Assess the level of preparedness of pre-service teachers for handling diverse learners in inclusive classrooms among colleges of education in Osun state.
4. Identify challenges in implementing inclusive education practices in Colleges of Education in Osun State.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. To what extent are capacity building initiatives implemented for inclusive education in Colleges of Education in Osun State?
2. How has the curriculum in teacher preparation programmes been transformed to accommodate inclusive education in colleges of education in Osun state?
3. What is the level of preparedness of pre-service teachers to handle inclusive classrooms in colleges of education in Osun state?
4. What are the challenges faced in the implementation of inclusive education practices in colleges of education in Osun state?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses will guide the study:
 H0₁: There is no significant relationship between capacity building initiatives and pre-service teachers’ preparedness for inclusive education among colleges of education in Osun state.
 H0₂: There is no significant difference in the level of curriculum transformation among colleges of education in Osun State.
 H0₃: There is no significant difference in the pre-service teachers’ competence influence and inclusive education in colleges of education in Osun state.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a descriptive survey design, which is appropriate for gathering information on current practices, perceptions, and challenges related to capacity building and curriculum transformation for inclusive education. The target population comprises all teacher educators and final-year pre-service teachers in public Colleges of Education in Osun State. These institutions include: Osun State College of Education, Ilesa, Ila-Orangun and Federal College of Education, Iwo. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select: 90 final-year pre-service teachers (30) from each institution. 60 teacher educators (20) from each institution. This makes a total sample of 150 respondents. A self-structured questionnaire titled “Capacity Building and Curriculum Transformation for Inclusive Education Questionnaire (CBCTIEQ)” was developed and used for the study. It consists of five sections: Section A: Demographic data, Section B: Capacity building initiatives. Section C: Curriculum transformation practices, Section D: Teacher preparedness for inclusive education, Section E: Challenges and opportunities. The questionnaire used a 4-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree – Strongly Disagree). The face, content and construct validity of the instrument was ensured by expert and specialists in Educational Research, Inclusive Education, Test and Measurement and English all from Osun state college of Ila-Orangun. A pilot study was conducted using pre-service teachers and educators from Emmanuel Alayande college of education, Oyo, and reliability coefficient was determined using Cronbach’s Alpha, with a threshold of 0.70 for acceptance. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) was used to answer the research questions while inferential statistics such as Pearson’s correlation and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level.

RESULTS

Research Question I: To what extent are capacity building initiatives implemented for inclusive education in Colleges of Education in Osun State?

Item	Statement Summary	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1	I have received formal training on inclusive education.	2.4	0.9	Below moderate
2	Workshops on inclusive teaching methods are regularly organized.	2.2	0.8	Low
3	There is ongoing professional development for teacher educators.	2.5	0.7	Moderate
4	I feel confident managing an inclusive classroom.	2.8	0.9	Moderate
5	I am competent in using assistive technology for teaching.	2.0	0.6	Low

From the analysis above, the mean values ($M < 3.0$) indicate a generally low to moderate level of capacity building for inclusive education. Therefore, capacity building efforts are limited and inconsistent. Most respondents report minimal exposure to structured inclusive education training.

Research Question 2: How has the curriculum in teacher preparation programmes been transformed to accommodate inclusive education?

Item	Statement Summary	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1	The curriculum promotes equity and diversity in learning.	2.3	0.8	Low
2	Teaching materials reflect the needs of diverse learners.	2.6	0.9	Moderate
3	Our College provides access to special education resources.	2.4	0.8	Low

From the above, the analysis shows that curriculum components partially reflect inclusive values but lack systemic integration. Therefore, curriculum transformation towards inclusion is emerging but lacks depth and consistency across institutions. However, the provision of special education resources is still lacking, confirming that inclusive curriculum transformation is in early stages.

Research Question 3: What is the level of preparedness of pre-service teachers to handle inclusive classrooms?

Item	Statement Summary	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1	I can differentiate instruction to accommodate all learners.	2.7	0.9	Moderate
2	I understand policies guiding inclusive education.	2.9	0.8	Moderate
3	Pre-service teachers are motivated to teach inclusively.	3.1	0.6	High

From the analysis above, teachers feel moderately prepared for inclusive teaching, though there are gaps in instructional differentiation and application of policy.

Research Question 4: What are the challenges faced in the implementation of inclusive education practices in Colleges of Education?

Item	Statement Summary	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1	Lack of instructional materials affects inclusive teaching.	2.1	0.9	Low
2	Large class sizes hinder personalized learning.	2.4	0.7	Low
3	There is institutional support for inclusive teaching innovation.	2.0	0.6	Low

From the above, the analysis shows significant challenges in implementing inclusive education, primarily due to limited instructional materials, overcrowded classrooms, and weak institutional support. These findings emphasize the need for systemic investment and policy enforcement to address infrastructural and institutional barriers.

Hypothesis Testing

H0: There is no significant relationship between capacity building initiatives and pre-service teachers' preparedness for inclusive education.

Pearson $r = 0.64, p < 0.05$

Therefore, the hypotheses is rejected which shows that there is significant positive relationship between capacity building initiatives and pre-service teachers' preparedness for inclusive education.

H0: There is no significant difference in the level of curriculum transformation among Colleges of Education in Osun State.

ANOVA result: $F(1,98) = 4.23, p = 0.03$

Therefore, the hypotheses is rejected which shows that significant difference exists in the level of curriculum transformation among Colleges of Education in Osun State.

H0: There is no significant difference in the pre-service teachers' competence influence and inclusive education.

Pearson $r = 0.58, p < 0.05$

Therefore, the hypotheses is rejected which shows that there is significant difference in the pre-service teachers' competence influence and inclusive education influences competence.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings from the survey indicate that while Colleges of Education in Osun State have initiated some capacity building efforts, these are not systematic or sustained. A majority of teacher educators and pre-service teachers reported low exposure to inclusive education content, this align with [6] assertion that Nigerian colleges need structural support for inclusion. Furthermore, the study also shows that curriculum content remains largely traditional, with limited emphasis on inclusive pedagogy or special needs education. This corroborates with [8] finding that curriculum reform is yet to align with global inclusive education standards. Interestingly, the outcome of the research also revealed that respondents acknowledged the importance of inclusive education but cited lack of practical training, large class sizes, and insufficient learning aids as critical barriers. These challenges mirror the broader structural issues in Nigeria's teacher education system as highlighted by [4].

Recent studies in Nigeria and sub-Saharan Africa reveal mixed results in teacher preparation for inclusive education. For example, [9] found that most Colleges of Education lack structured modules on inclusion, while [8] showed that teachers who underwent inclusive training were better at classroom management and learner support.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The outcome of this study could be of immense benefit to policy maker, as it would provide empirical evidence that can inform policymakers on the state of inclusive teacher education in Nigeria and guide reforms in line with sustainable development goals. The study will help to identify practical challenges faced by teacher educators and pre-service teachers, thereby providing insights for interventions in curriculum transformation and professional development. The outcome of the study would enrich scholarship on capacity building and inclusive education, highlighting the intersection between teacher preparation, curriculum transformation, and sustainable educational practices. It would also help by aligning with UNESCO's agenda of inclusive and equitable education for all, this study would finally contribute to international discourse and offers lessons applicable to other sub-Saharan African contexts.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

While this study provides important insights, several challenges were faced in the course of the research;

1. The study was conducted in Colleges of Education within Osun State only due to the time constraints and shortage of fund in carrying out the research, results may not be generalizable to all Nigerian institutions.
2. The reliance on self-reported data through questionnaires was also seen to be bias, as participants could provide socially desirable responses. However, other means can be as well utilize.
3. The sampled size was 150 respondents, the study can still be engaged with a larger sample across multiple states that would provide stronger generalizations.
4. The study was descriptive and cross-sectional in nature, and therefore cannot establish a causal relationship. However, studies could adopt a longitudinal design, cover multiple states, and include interviews or classroom observations for richer insights.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that although Colleges of Education in Osun State recognize the importance of inclusive education, capacity building and curriculum transformation efforts are still in their infancy. Teacher preparation programs are not yet robust enough to equip pre-service teachers with the skills

and competencies needed to foster inclusive and sustainable learning environments. Without intentional investment in training, policy implementation, and curriculum overhaul, the vision of inclusive education will remain largely unfulfilled.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Colleges should integrate special needs education, differentiated instruction, and inclusive strategies into their core teacher education curriculum.
2. Continuous professional development should be institutionalized for both pre-service and in-service teachers on inclusive pedagogy.
3. Government and regulatory bodies must provide funding, infrastructure, and technical support for the implementation of inclusive programs.
4. NCE and College academic boards should periodically review and update curricula to reflect inclusive and sustainable development goals.
5. Colleges of Education should collaborate with NGOs, inclusive education specialists, and international bodies to enrich faculty and student exposure.

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